

INTEGRATION OF TEACHING OF SPECIALISTS WITH PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract: this article talks about the integration of the teaching of specialty and specialty subjects with pedagogical technologies and its impact on the quality of the educational process in higher educational institutions.

Key words: specialized subjects, technological education, integration, pedagogical technology.

Introduction:

Today, using information and communication technologies effectively in the educational process, it is necessary to create the most modern types of training manuals, textbooks and collections, to ensure the continuity of scientifically based knowledge and to maintain appropriate integration in the fields of science, in the teaching of specialized subjects. The appropriate use of pedagogical technologies, the development of innovative forms of teaching to achieve effective results, and the use of new methods of conducting practical training organized in higher education institutions require high creativity from specialists.

There are a number of problems that are important to be solved and they are waiting for their solution. A clear example of this is the insufficient supply of manuals, teaching methods, textbooks for the organization of the technology education process, and the fact that modern technologies and the process of modernization in the teaching of technology science are very slow.

There is a lack of scientific and methodological resources related to the technological approach in the organization of educational processes on technology education, there are a lot of topics that are not integrated in the existing manuals and methodological complexes, and materials that do not provide coherence, especially they do not meet today's requirements. mobility, compactness, and the fact that it does not reflect modern technologies causes a number of difficulties. The creation of electronic teaching-methodical complexes serves not only to modernize the educational process, but also to increase its effectiveness.

In today's era of advanced information and communication technologies, it is necessary to improve the educational system, modernize the educational process, bring scientific and methodological manuals and collections to a certain integrity, facilitate their use, and improve the organization of training for students. Our main goal is to expand the access to pedagogical technologies and eliminate the problems that await their solution.

According to the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 20, 2017 No. PD-2909 "On measures to further develop the higher education system", each higher education institution is the world's leading scientific and educational institutions establishment of close cooperation relations with the educational process, wide introduction of advanced pedagogical technologies, educational programs and teaching-methodical

materials based on international educational standards, educational-pedagogical activities, master-classes to actively attract highly qualified teachers and scientists from foreign partner educational institutions to training courses, to organize internships for master's students, young teachers and scientific staff of higher educational institutions of our republic on their basis, professors organization of retraining and professional development of teachers, wide introduction of new pedagogical technologies and teaching methods in the educational process, curricula and programs of higher education, qualitative renewal of the master's scientific-educational process and modern organizational further improvement based on the introduction of forms, equipping higher education institutions with modern information and communication technologies, world educational resources of students, teachers and young researchers of higher education institutions, electronic catalogs and databases of modern scientific literature a number of tasks such as expansion of access possibilities have been set. The purpose of this is to perfect the educational process at the level of world standards, which directly involves the proper organization of the educational process and raising the educational efficiency to higher levels.

In the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 6, 2020 No. PD-4884 "On additional measures to further improve the education system", fundamental reform of the education system, education We can see that the revision of all the elements of the education process, the preparation of the new National program adapted to our national values is a process aimed at perfection, taking into account the elements of the educational process and its aspects.

The essence of education is the process of transferring the life experiences collected by adults to the next generation in a specific purpose-oriented and organized manner as a result of the development of the public consciousness, production and labor productivity in a given society in social relations.

Before applying various pedagogical technologies and their evaluation criteria to the educational process, we must control the implementation of several principles that express the technological essence of pedagogical activity. The principles of pedagogical technology work in interdependence, and it is important to take into account its content when designing the pedagogical process. One of the principles of pedagogical technology is that in order for pupils and students to fully understand the given knowledge, it is necessary to create a problem situation in the lesson. If we arouse interest in the knowledge that is intended to be given to the students, and then start imparting the knowledge, the effect will be high.

In order to formulate a problem situation, giving an example from life, students are asked a question. Students are expected to answer the question at least a little. If you wait for a long time, the interest in the lesson will decrease and the allocated time will not be used effectively. Therefore, regardless of whether it is correct or incorrect, after we hear the answer of one or two students, the correct answer is given during their answer. Then the students will understand well the knowledge given in the lesson. In order for the students to keep the given knowledge in their thoughts, the knowledge is repeated at least 4-5 times in different ways. Then the knowledge acquired in the lesson will enter the memory box. This is a law that scientists of pedagogy and psychology have determined after conducting a number of studies. That is, in order for quantity to change to quality, it has to be returned 4-5 times, sometimes 6-7 times. In order to create skills on the basis of knowledge that has been understood and preserved in thinking, knowledge must be supported in practice. If the

training is related to the acquisition of theoretical knowledge, it is necessary to ask the students to return and tell all the knowledge that has been given to understand, and of course to strengthen this knowledge at home through a series of exercises. If students understand, keep in their thoughts, and apply the given knowledge at the same time, then the students will understand and master this knowledge.

In our opinion, it is impossible to consider new pedagogical technology as a separate branch of pedagogy or as a system aimed only at optimizing educational practice. Pedagogical technology determines the directions of activity within the framework of combining theoretical and practical research in this field. The essence of the research here is modernization based on the study of the elements that make up the pedagogical system. The reason is that the organization of any educational process reflects one or another pedagogical system. So, pedagogical technology is a project of a certain pedagogical system that can be put into practice.

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